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КЛИНИКО-НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВЕРТЕБРОБАЗИЛЯРНОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТИ В ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ОТ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ ЭТИОПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Вертебробазилярная недостаточность (ВБН) является распространенным цереброваскулярным заболеванием, различные формы которого имеют различные клинические проявления. В данном исследовании три типа ВБН: атеросклеротически-гипертензивный, мигренозный и формы, связанные с сосудистыми аномалиями, сравнивались по клиническим и неврологическим характеристикам. Результаты показали, что каждый тип ВБН имеет определенное клиническое течение. Результаты данного исследования служат для улучшения клинической оценки и дифференциальной диагностики ВБН.

Ключевые слова: вертебробазилярная недостаточность, клинические и неврологические симптомы, головокружение, вестибулярные расстройства, мигрень, сосудистые аномалии.

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CLINICAL-NEUROLOGICAL FEATURES IN VERTEBROBASILAR INSUFFICIENCY DEPENDENT ON VARIOUS ETIOPATHOGENETIC FACTORS

ANNOTATION

Vertebrobasilar insufficiency (VBI) is a common cerebrovascular disease, the different forms of which have different clinical manifestations. In this study, three types of VBI: atherosclerotic-hypertensive, migraine, and forms associated with vascular anomalies were compared in terms of clinical and neurological characteristics. The results showed that each type of VBI has a specific clinical course. The results of this study serve to improve the clinical assessment and differential diagnosis of VBI.

Keywords: Vertebrobasilar insufficiency, clinical and neurological symptoms, dizziness, vestibular disorders, migraine, vascular anomalies.

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TURLI ETIOPATOGENETIK OMILLARGA BOG'LIQ VERTEBROBAZILYAR YETISHMOVCHILIKDA KLINIK-NEVROLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Vertebrobazilyar yetishmovchilik (VBY) – keng tarqalgan serebrovaskulyar kasallik bo'lib, uning turli shakllari har xil klinik belgilarga ega. Ushbu tadqiqotda VBYning uch turi: aterosklerotik-gipertonik, migrenoz va qon tomir anomaliyalari bilan bog'liq shakllar klinik-nevrologik xususiyatlari bo'yicha solishtirildi. Natijalar VBYning har bir turi o'ziga xos klinik kechishiga ega ekanligini ko'rsatdi. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari vertebrobazilyar yetishmovchilikni klinik jihatdan to'g'ri baholash va differensial diagnostika jarayonini takomillashtirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Vertebrobazilyar yetishmovchilik, klinik-nevrologik simptomlar, bosh aylanishi, vestibulyar buzilishlar, migren, qon tomir anomaliyalari.

Vertebrobasilar insufficiency (VBI) is one of the most common pathologies in modern neurology, which occurs as a result of ischemic damage to the spinal arterial system. This condition is associated with insufficient blood supply to the vertebral and basilar arteries, which supply the posterior part of the brain - the cerebellum, occipital lobes of the cerebral cortex, optic chiasm and brainstem, and causes a variety

of clinical symptoms in patients [1,2]. According to epidemiological studies, vertebrobasilar system strokes account for approximately 20–30% of all acute cerebral circulatory insufficiency [3]. The chronic form of VBI is also widespread among the population, especially in people over 50 years of age. In particular, risk factors such as arterial hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes mellitus and smoking significantly

contribute to the development of this pathology [4]. The clinical presentation of VBI is highly variable and is characterized by symptoms such as dizziness, ataxia, visual disturbances, dysarthria, and dysphagia [5]. The mechanism of occurrence of these symptoms depends on the etiopathogenetic type of VBI. Studies have identified three main etiological types of VBI:

1. **Atherosclerotic-hypertensive VBI** is a form that occurs more often in elderly patients and is associated with thickening, stenosis, and thrombosis of the vertebral and basilar arteries as a result of atherosclerosis and arterial hypertension [6]. Vestibular dysfunction, cognitive impairment, and balance disorders are often observed in this type of patient.
2. **Migrainous VBI** is a condition that occurs mainly in young patients and develops as part of a migraine headache. In this case, VBI is transient and characterized by visual disturbances, dizziness, and paroxysmal neurological symptoms [7].
3. **Vascular anomalies-related VBI** develops as a result of congenital or acquired vascular anomalies (e.g., fibromuscular dysplasia, arterial dissections). In this type, symptoms often occur in response to changes in head position [8].

Currently, a thorough study of the clinical and neurological features of VBI and the identification of the main differences between different etiopathogenetic types is of great scientific and practical importance. Because VBI is difficult to diagnose and can sometimes be confused with other neurological diseases. For example, conditions such as inner ear pathologies, Parkinson's disease, or orthostatic hypotension can also manifest with symptoms similar to VBI [9]. Therefore, it is necessary to thoroughly analyze the clinical features of VBI, differentiate these different etiological forms, and improve differential diagnosis [10].

The aim of the study is to analyze the clinical and neurological features observed in different etiopathogenetic types of vertebrobasilar insufficiency, to identify specific forms of symptom manifestation, and to show the differences between these types.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study involved 75 patients with vertebrobasilar insufficiency (VBI) and 15 healthy controls. The age of the study participants ranged from 35 to 65 years, and their gender and comorbidities were also taken into account.

Patients were divided into the following etiopathogenetic groups:

1. Atherosclerotic-hypertensive VBI – 25 patients
2. Migraine-associated VBI – 25 patients
3. Vascular anomalies associated with VBI – 25 patients

4. Control group – 15 healthy patients

Methods of examining patients

During the study, patients were examined using clinical-neurological, subjective, and functional scales.

1. Clinical and neurological examination

The following indicators were evaluated in each patient:

Neurological examination – Cranial nerves, pyramidal signs, cerebellar functions, reflexes and muscle tone were assessed.

Vestibular tests – Horizontal and vertical nystagmus, Romberg test were performed.

Characteristics of dizziness – systemic or non-systemic, duration of episodes

Visual disturbances – diplopia, black spots before the eyes

Cognitive and autonomic symptoms – memory loss, sleep disturbances, irritability

2. Functional assessment scales

Dizziness Handicap Inventory (DHI) – Assesses patients' complaints of dizziness and vestibular dysfunction

Verny Scale (VSS) – Assesses the severity of dizziness and vestibular dysfunction.

SF-36 (36-Item Short Form Survey) – Used to assess physical and mental aspects of quality of life.

RESEARCH RESULTS

1. Demographics of groups

The Atherosclerotic + Hypertensive VBI group included 25 patients. Their mean age was 65±5 years, with 64% men and 36% women. The Atherosclerotic and Hypertensive VBI group was more common in patients over 40 years of age. Men predominated in this group, since atherosclerosis and hypertension develop earlier in men than in women. The Migraine-associated VBI group included 25 patients, with a mean age of 45±7 years. The number of women was higher, 68%, and men were 32%. The Migrainous VBI group included patients aged 30-45 years. The number of women was higher in this group, since migraine is 2-3 times more common in women than in men. The VBI group associated with vascular anomalies also included 25 patients, with a mean age of 50±6. In this group, 60% were men and 40% were women. VBI associated with vascular anomalies occurred in patients of all ages, but the number of men was slightly higher than that of women. The control group consisted of 15 healthy individuals, whose mean age was 47±5 years. The number of men and women was equal, almost 50% each. The control group consisted of healthy individuals, whose age ranged from 35 to 50 years (Table 1).

Demographic characteristics of patients in groups

Table 1

Groups	Number of participants	Mean age (M±SD)	Male (%)	Female (%)
Atherosclerotic + Hypertonic VBI	25	65±5	64%	36%
Migraine-related VBI	25	45±7	32%	68%
Vascular anomalies associated with VBI	25	50±6	60%	40%
Control group	15	47±5	52%	48%

3. Neurological symptoms

Patients' complaints differed depending on the etiopathogenetic type of vertebrobasilar insufficiency. In patients of the Atherosclerotic + Hypertonic VBI group, dizziness, headache, tinnitus, short-term visual impairment, and general weakness were more common. Among male patients, high blood pressure, fatigue, and cognitive decline were

more common, while in women, migraine and vegetative dystonia symptoms were observed. In patients of the migraine VBI group, migraine headaches, nausea, sensitivity to light, and balance disorders were more common. These symptoms were more pronounced in women than in men. In patients of the VBI group associated with vascular anomalies, headache and weakness were the leading symptoms, and acute dizziness was more common in men, and sleep disturbances and nervousness were more common in women (Table 2).

Subjective neurological symptoms of patients

Table 2

Symptom	Atherosclerotic + Hypertonic VBI (n=25)		Migraine-related VBI (n=25)		Vascular anomalies associated with VBI (n=25)		Control group (n=15)	
	Male n=16	Female n=9	Male n=8	Female n=17	Male n=15	Female n=10	Male n=13	Female n=12
Dizziness	9 (75%)	11 (85%)	8 (73%)	11 (79%)	9 (69%)	9 (75%)	1 (12%)	1 (14%)
Headache	10 (83%)	11 (85%)	10 (91%)	13 (93%)	8 (62%)	7 (58%)	2 (25%)	1 (14%)
Ringings in the ears	8 (67%)	10 (77%)	7 (64%)	9 (64%)	7 (54%)	7 (58%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Nausea and vomiting	6 (50%)	7 (54%)	6 (55%)	9 (64%)	5 (38%)	5 (42%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Balance disorder	7 (58%)	8 (62%)	6 (55%)	8 (57%)	6 (46%)	6 (50%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Decreased vision	5 (42%)	6 (46%)	4 (36%)	6 (43%)	4 (31%)	5 (42%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Sleep disorder	6 (50%)	8 (62%)	6 (55%)	7 (50%)	5 (38%)	6 (50%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Fatigue	8 (67%)	8 (62%)	7 (64%)	8 (57%)	6 (46%)	7 (58%)	1 (12%)	1 (14%)
Mood disorder	6 (50%)	7 (54%)	6 (55%)	8 (57%)	5 (38%)	6 (50%)	1 (12%)	1 (14%)
Memory loss	4 (33%)	6 (46%)	4 (36%)	5 (36%)	4 (31%)	4 (33%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)

The results of the neurological examination were different for each group and reflected changes associated with the state of the central and peripheral nervous system. In the atherosclerotic + hypertensive VBI group, gait tremor, nystagmus, dysarthria, and the appearance of pathological reflexes were observed. In the migraine VBI group,

photophobia, symptoms of encephalopathy, vegetative disorders, and changes in muscle tone were detected. In the VBI group associated with vascular anomalies, dystonia, reflex asymmetry, decreased muscle tone, ataxia, and vegetative disorders were observed (Table 3).

Objective neurological symptoms of patients

Table 3

Symptom	Atherosclerotic + Hypertonic VBI (n=25)		Migraine-related VBI (n=25)		Vascular anomalies associated with VBI (n=25)		Control group (n=15)	
	Male n=16	Female n=9	Male n=8	Female n=17	Erkaklar n=15	Male n=16	Female n=9	Male n=8
Nystagmus	4 (33%)	6 (46%)	5 (45%)	6 (43%)	4 (31%)	5 (42%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Movement disorder	5 (42%)	7 (54%)	6 (55%)	8 (57%)	5 (38%)	5 (42%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Balance disorders	7 (58%)	8 (62%)	5 (45%)	8 (57%)	6 (46%)	6 (50%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Akinetic rigid syndrome	4 (33%)	5 (38%)	4 (36%)	6 (43%)	3 (23%)	5 (42%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Pseudobulbar syndromes	4 (33%)	4 (31%)	3 (27%)	4 (29%)	3 (23%)	3 (25%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Sensory disturbances	5 (42%)	5 (38%)	4 (36%)	5 (36%)	4 (31%)	4 (33%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Speech disorders	3 (25%)	3 (23%)	3 (27%)	4 (29%)	2 (15%)	3 (25%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)
Other symptoms	2 (17%)	3 (23%)	2 (18%)	2 (14%)	1 (8%)	2 (17%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)

3. Functional assessment scales

3.1 Dizziness Handicap Inventory (DHI) results

The highest DHI score in the atherosclerotic + hypertensive VBI group indicated that these patients were more likely to experience functional and psychological limitations due to dizziness. The DHI scores were relatively lower in the migraine VBI group, indicating that

dizziness in these patients was episodic. In the VBI group associated with vascular anomalies, the impact of dizziness on functional and physical aspects was high, but the emotional component was less pronounced. The DHI scores in the control group were minimal,

indicating that dizziness and its impact on quality of life were absent in healthy individuals (Table 4).

Patients' Dizziness Handicap Inventory (DHI) results Table 4

Indicators	Atherosclerotic + Hypertonic VBI (n=25)	Migraine-related VBI (n=25)	Vascular anomalies associated with VBI (n=25)	Control group (n=15)
Total score (M±SD)	56.8 ± 8.3	48.2 ± 7.5	51.4 ± 6.9	10.5 ± 3.2
Functional subscale (F)	20.1 ± 3.5	18.4 ± 3.2	19.0 ± 3.3	2.4 ± 1.1
Emotional subscale (E)	19.6 ± 2.9	15.8 ± 3.1	16.9 ± 2.7	3.0 ± 1.2
Physical subscale (P)	17.1 ± 2.8	14.0 ± 2.6	15.5 ± 2.9	5.1 ± 1.3

3.2 Verny Scale (VSS) results

The highest VSS score in the atherosclerotic + hypertensive VBI group indicated that these patients had the most severe dizziness and vestibular symptoms. In the migraine VBI group, symptoms were relatively mild, especially tinnitus and neurovegetative disorders were less pronounced. In the VBI group associated with vascular anomalies,

symptoms were moderate, vestibular disorders and tinnitus were more common. In the control group, VSS scores were minimal, and dizziness and vestibular symptoms were almost not detected in healthy individuals (Table 5).

Patients' Verny Scale (VSS) results Table 5

Indicators	Atherosclerotic + Hypertonic VBI (n=25)	Migraine-related VBI (n=25)	Vascular anomalies associated with VBI (n=25)	Control group (n=15)
Total score (M±SD)	9.2 ± 1.8	7.5 ± 1.6	8.1 ± 1.5	2.3 ± 0.9
Dizziness	3.6 ± 0.7	2.9 ± 0.6	3.2 ± 0.6	0.8 ± 0.3
Tinnitus	2.5 ± 0.5	1.8 ± 0.4	2.1 ± 0.5	0.4 ± 0.2
Vision disorders	1.8 ± 0.4	1.5 ± 0.3	1.7 ± 0.3	0.3 ± 0.1
Coordination disorders	2.1 ± 0.5	1.8 ± 0.4	1.9 ± 0.5	0.5 ± 0.2
Neurovegetative symptoms	2.0 ± 0.4	1.6 ± 0.3	1.8 ± 0.3	0.3 ± 0.1

3.3 Differences between groups in SF-36 scores

In the Atherosclerotic + Hypertensive VBI group, the PCS and MCS scores were the lowest, indicating a significant deterioration in the physical and mental quality of life of these patients. In the Migrainous VBI group, all scores were relatively high, indicating a moderate impact

on quality of life. In the VBI group associated with vascular anomalies, a decrease in physical and social functioning was observed. In the control group, the SF-36 scores were the highest, indicating good physical and mental health in healthy individuals (Table 6).

Results of patients on the SF-36 scale Table 6

Indicators	Atherosclerotic + Hypertonic VBI (n=25)	Migraine-related VBI (n=25)	Vascular anomalies associated with VBI (n=25)	Control group (n=15)
Physical activity (PA)	58.3 ± 8.5	72.1 ± 6.7	64.5 ± 7.2	90.2 ± 5.1
Physical limitations (RP)	45.6 ± 7.1	61.8 ± 5.9	50.4 ± 6.8	87.3 ± 4.9
Pain (BP)	54.2 ± 6.3	68.5 ± 5.2	60.1 ± 5.9	88.4 ± 4.6
General Health (GH)	47.8 ± 7.5	63.2 ± 6.1	55.6 ± 6.4	86.7 ± 5.0
Vitality (VT)	50.1 ± 5.8	65.7 ± 4.9	57.3 ± 5.5	84.5 ± 4.8
Social Activities (SA)	52.7 ± 6.2	68.9 ± 5.5	58.2 ± 6.1	89.1 ± 4.4
Emotional restraints (RE)	48.6 ± 7.0	60.4 ± 6.3	53.1 ± 6.8	85.6 ± 4.7
Mental Health (MH)	46.3 ± 6.9	62.8 ± 5.7	55.4 ± 6.2	87.9 ± 5.2
Physical Component (PCS)	51.2 ± 6.7	67.5 ± 5.3	58.9 ± 6.1	88.1 ± 4.9

Indicators	Atherosclerotic + Hypertensive VBI (n=25)	Migraine-related VBI (n=25)	Vascular anomalies associated with VBI (n=25)	Control group (n=15)
Mental component (MCS)	49.4 ± 7.1	64.1 ± 5.8	56.7 ± 6.4	86.3 ± 4.6

CONCLUSIONS

1. Atherosclerotic + Hypertensive VBI usually affects older patients and presents with chronic symptoms. Migrainous VBI is more common in younger women and presents with migraine attacks. Although VBI associated with vascular anomalies occurs in patients of all ages, vegetative and balance disorders predominate clinically.
2. In the atherosclerotic + hypertensive VBI group, dizziness, headache, tinnitus, short-term visual disturbances, and general weakness were the most common symptoms. In the migraine VBI group, migraine attacks, photophobia, nausea, and balance disorders prevailed. In VBI patients associated with vascular anomalies, headache and general weakness were noted as the main complaints.
3. Nystagmus, dysarthria, gait disturbance, and reflex changes were observed in the atherosclerotic + hypertensive VBI group. Autonomic

disorders, encephalopathy symptoms, and muscle tone changes were observed in the migraine VBI group. Reflex asymmetry, dystonia, and ataxia were observed in the VBI group associated with vascular anomalies.

4. Vestibular symptoms and quality of life differed significantly in different etiopathogenetic types of vertebrobasilar insufficiency. Patients with atherosclerotic + hypertensive VBI had severe dizziness, balance disorders, and tinnitus, and the greatest decrease in quality of life was observed. In patients with migraine VBI, vestibular symptoms were episodic, and the quality of life was relatively well preserved. In the VBI group associated with vascular anomalies, vestibular symptoms were accompanied by neuromuscular disorders. In the control group, vestibular symptoms were almost absent and the quality of life was high.

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